

Compilation of dissemination and communication materials

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

*LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE** strategy (Figure 1) to*

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder,**

Figure 1 Push-Pull-Enable Strategy

participatory approach involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs** (LLs) and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

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List of abbreviations

D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DIY	Do It Yourself
ECLLD	European Coordination Let's Liberate Diversity
ECO-PB	The European Consortium for Organic Plant Breeding
IFOAM OE	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements- IFOAM Organics Europe
IPS	IPS Konzalting
KIS	Kmetijski Inštitut Slovenije
MUFPP	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact
PEDR	Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results
PSR	ProSpecieRara
RSR	Rete Semi Rurali

Glossary

Term	Definition
PUSH-PULL-ENABLE Strategy	A strategy to enhance the organic seed sector by increasing supply (PUSH), increasing demand (PULL), and creating a favourable policy environment (ENABLE). This strategy is fundamental to the LiveSeeding project's approach.
Living Labs	Real-life test environments where stakeholders co-create, develop, and validate innovations. LiveSeeding involves 17 local Living Labs across Europe.
The European Consortium for Organic Plant Breeding	A network of organizations focused on organic plant breeding in Europe. Context: ECO-PB is one of the key networks involved in LiveSeeding. ECO-PB is one of the key networks involved in LiveSeeding.
Plan for the Exploitation Dissemination and	A strategic plan outlining how the project results will be disseminated and exploited. PEDR includes guidelines for partners on using communication materials

Communication of Results	
Organic Heterogeneous Material	Plant reproductive material that is genetically and phenotypically diverse. LiveSeeding addresses how OHM can be notified and utilized in organic farming.
Plant Reproductive Material	A centralized platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material. This database is one of the tools developed by LiveSeeding to support the organic seed market

Summary

This deliverable provides a digest (or a collection of) the communication and dissemination materials developed and broadcasted from the LiveSeeding inception until month 24 (September 2024). These include:

- Communication materials and tools prepared to ensure consistent and effective communication throughout the consortium: the project's visual identity, templates for various documents, a general project leaflet, a roll-up banner, a concise project pitch, a general project presentation, an official project video, short videos with project experts, and articles for general media.*
- dissemination materials aimed to transfer the project's findings, outcomes, and innovations to various target audiences.*

This deliverable highlights the importance of uniform visual identity to enhance the project's recognition and outlines the materials and methods used for the communication and dissemination of the LiveSeeding project. Moreover, it showcases key communication channels that are regularly being used to broadcast (OR circulate) materials among the target audience, and to engage with the stakeholders.

1. Introduction

Deliverable 7.4 “Compilation of dissemination and communication materials” is the first digest/recollection and covers project work until month 24 (September 2024). A further version of this deliverable will be submitted at the end of the project in September 2026 (month 48) in Deliverable 7.8 “Compilation of dissemination and communication materials”.

This is a public document that compiles all communication and dissemination materials that have been developed during the first two years of the project aiming to ensure that all produced materials are comprehensively included and easily accessible in one unified document. Additionally, this deliverable outlines the key communication channels that are consistently utilized to distribute these materials to the target audience and engage with the stakeholders. Some of the materials and channels presented as part of this deliverable have already been developed in the initial stages of the project, and have therefore been described in previous deliverables, such as the first version of the “Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results (PEDR)” and [D7.2 “LIVESEEDING project website and social media”](#) in month 6 (e.g. project pitch and general project presentation, social media channels, website) together with the guidelines for partners on how and where to use these materials.

Following chapters of this deliverable will provide a detailed overview of the project’s key communication materials (general project leaflet/brochure, roll up banner, project pitch, general project PowerPoint presentation, official project video, videos with project experts, articles for general media), key communication channels (social media channels, website, newsletters, YouTube channel) and key dissemination materials (deliverables, scientific publications, practice abstracts, policy briefs) that have been produced at the time of writing of this deliverable.

Efficient communication and dissemination are crucial for promoting the project's objectives, ensuring visibility, and engaging stakeholders across various platforms and channels.

2. Overview of key dissemination and communication materials

In the initial stages of the project, various communication materials and tools have been developed in order to ensure efficient and effective communication in order to reach the target audiences in a diversified manner. Special emphasis was placed on establishing basic visual standards of the LiveSeeding project (logo, symbol, colours, typography) to ensure distinctive visibility of the project, as well as consistency of communication by the entire consortium. For this reason, a set of different templates was prepared together with guidelines for visual identity were prepared and uploaded on the project SharePoint for use of all consortium partners.

Key project's communication materials include:

- general project leaflet/brochure
- roll up banner
- project pitch
- general project PowerPoint presentation
- official project video
- videos with project experts
- articles for general media

Key project's communication channels include:

- social media channels
- website
- newsletters
- YouTube channel

Key project's dissemination materials include:

- deliverables
- scientific publications
- practice abstracts
- policy briefs

3. Key communication materials

3.1 LiveSeeding visual identity

Streamlined and uniform communication enhances the project's recognition. Therefore, the consistent use of the official logo, symbol, colors, and typography of the project in all project-related communication and dissemination materials and activities is of great importance.

All elements of the LiveSeeding visual identity (Figure 2) are available for project partners on the SharePoint in the folder "Project official docs and templates" → "[Visual Identity](#)."

- Symbol & Logo: The symbol represents a seed sprouting from the soil and features the project name in blue and green. The logo and symbol package include several variations for different backgrounds and document types. The LiveSeeding symbol can be used alone, as it is a highly recognizable part of the visual identity.
- Typography/Fonts: The official project font is GADUGI, which can be used in regular, bold, and italic forms.
- Colors: Blue and green are the primary colors of the project, chosen to create a distinct and strong visual identity.
- Donors' acknowledgement,

Guidelines for the project's visual identity have been prepared in the form of a "[Basic visual standards](#)" document, stored on the LiveSeeding SharePoint.

Figure 2 Visual identity elements

3.2 Templates

To ensure consistency, various templates have been produced that ensure all reports and project related documents have a uniform look, reinforcing brand recognition and visual identity and also facilitate the work of partners. Consistent use of the project logo, colors, and typography across reports makes them easily identifiable and enhances the overall clarity and readability of the documents.

These templates include: deliverable template, event invite template, letterhead template, presentation template, etc.

Templates can be found on SharePoint in the folder "Project official docs and templates" → "[Templates](#)" and some of the templates are listed in **Annex I** of this deliverable.

3.3 General project leaflet

A 4-page A5 format (bi-fold) project leaflet/brochure was produced in month 9 of the project (M9, June 2023). It contains general project information, such as the description of the main project objectives, project duration, consortium, geographical reach, and both textual and visual presentation of the Push-Pull-Enable methodology. All visual identity elements are integrated in the leaflet.

Elements of the leaflet are:

- **About**
- **Who is involved?**
- **Push-Pull-Enable methodology**
- **Innovative approach**
- **Follow us on (section for LiveSeeding communication channels)**
- **Partners' logos**

The leaflet was initially prepared in English (Figure 1), and then translated by project partners in 12 consortium languages (German, Greek, Spanish in 2 versions), Italian, Portuguese, French, Hungarian, Dutch, Polish, Romanian, Slovenian and Croatian) for a total of 5280 copies. It was shared with all project partners during the 2nd annual meeting in Poland (September 2023). A pdf version is also available in the project collaborative workspace (SharePoint) for partners to print further if needed.

Project leaflets in all consortium languages are listed in **Annex II**.

Digital version of the project leaflet has also been distributed over LiveSeeding social media channels, and English version (Figure 3) can be found on the project website under the [Resources](#) section.

Who is involved?

To deliver on such an ambitious goal, LiveSeeding brings together **37 organizations** covering whole value chain. This includes public and private research institutions and universities, seed producers, plant breeders, farmers, decision-makers and public authorities, processors and consumers operating in **16 European countries**.

Push-Pull-Enable methodology

Our work combines activities that increase both the **supply (PUSH)** and **demand (PULL)** of organic seeds and cultivars across the sector and feeds into the development of an enabling **policy environment (ENABLE)**.

Innovative approach

LiveSeeding follows a holistic, multi-actor and participatory approach. Various stakeholders are involved through:

- **17 LIVING LABS** bringing together breeders, consumers and citizens
- **3 established networks** of Organic Breeders (ECO-PB), Seed Savers and Community seed banks (ECLLD), and cities members of Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP).

Figure 3 General project leaflet in English

3.4 Project roll up banner

A Project roll up banner was also produced in month 9 of the project (M9, June 2023), together with the project leaflet.

The Roll up contains top line project to visually represent the main project information, in combination with basic visual identity elements of the project (logo, symbol, colors, lines). The roll up banner allows partners to make LiveSeeding visible at conferences, events, workshops and field days.

The roll up banner was initially developed in English and translated by project partners to 9 consortium languages (German, Greek, Spanish (3 versions), Italian (2 versions), Dutch, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian and Slovenian). Project roll up banners in all consortium languages are listed in **Annex III**.

Information provided on the roll up banner are:

- **Project duration**
- **Project budget**
- **Number of focus crops**
- **Number of partners**
- **Number of Living Labs**
- **Number of countries represented in the consortium**
- **Info on LiveSeeding social media channels and website**
- **Partners' logos**

At the time of writing this deliverable, the project roll up has been printed and distributed in 7 pieces among project partners, in various languages.

A pdf version is also available in the project collaborative workspace (SharePoint) for partners to print further if needed. Digital version of the project roll up has also been distributed over LiveSeeding social media channels, and English version (Figure 4) can be found on the project website under the [Resources](#) section.

Figure 4 Project roll up banner in English

3.5 Project pitch “LiveSeeding in a nutshell”

LiveSeeding is an innovation project based on scientific research, thus the terminology used can be complex for some stakeholders to understand. To address this, a short project "pitch" has been created in the initial stages of the project, outlining the project's core elements, main objectives, activities, and expected results. The pitch is designed to communicate the project in a language accessible to a wider audience outside the scientific community and it ensures consistent communication of the project to the public (divulgative communication tool).

A pitch is an effective method for brief and concise communication of key project ideas, aiming to spark interest in learning more about the project. Project partners can use it when communicating project activities to various stakeholder groups through different dissemination and communication methods and channels. It can also serve as background information for media when sending press releases or approaching media outlets. The pitch, titled "LiveSeeding in a nutshell," (Figure 5) is provided in **Annex IV** and is available on LiveSeeding SharePoint in the section Project Overview and key docs, under the folder [Key Communication Materials](#).

Guidelines for partners for using the LiveSeeding pitch have also been addressed in the first version of Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results (PEDR).

LiveSeeding in a nutshell

LiveSeeding is a 4-year Innovation Action on organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe, which started in October 2022. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed. The project has a budget of 6.6 million Euro, funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). To deliver on such an ambitious goal, LiveSeeding brings together 37 organisations from a wide range of sectors operating in 16 European countries.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE** strategy to

- Enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (**PUSH**).
- Increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (**PULL**).
- Foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (**ENABLE**).

Figure 5 Project pitch

3.6 LiveSeeding general presentation

The PowerPoint presentation "LiveSeeding in a nutshell" is the official project presentation that all partners use for basic communication about the project (Figure 6) in a consistent fashion. Along with the project pitch, brochure, roll up banner and video, it forms the core of the key project communication materials. These materials should be used when attending meetings, speaking in public, developing additional materials, and generally communicating about the project. They ensure streamlined and consistent communication throughout the Consortium and the project's duration.

The presentation is available on SharePoint in the "Project overview and key docs" section, under "[Key Communication Materials](#)". Partners can use this as a basis and expand on it for their specific presentations related to project activities or outputs but should leave the original content unchanged. Partners may also translate it into their national languages, pending approval from the Communication Coordinator (and Project Coordinator/Scientific Team when appropriate).

Figure 6 Title slide of the general project presentation

3.7 Project official video

An official LiveSeeding project video “**LiveSeeding project-Transforming organic seed systems!**” (Figure 7) to communicate about the project, its objectives and activities to a broad audience has been produced and officially published on the 15th of April 2024 on the YouTube channel of the Communication Coordinator (IPS). Furthermore, the video was announced on all LiveSeeding social media channels, website and circulated to all project partners for further circulation.

The video summarizes the project’s key activities and objectives in three and a half minutes and emphasizes some of the project’s key messages for the target audience.

Being one of the core communication materials, partners are highly encouraged to share the video with the stakeholders during some online events, such as webinars and workshops, as well as to distribute it over their communication channels (social media channels, websites, etc.).

At the time of writing this deliverable, the video has reached 390 views. The video can be accessed by the following link: [Project official video.](#)

The video narratives are in English, however, to maximize the impact and to reach out to a bigger number of the stakeholders at the local level, partners have additionally translated the video captions to their national languages. The video captions are therefore available in German, Greek, Spanish, Italian, Polish, Hungarian and Portuguese.

Figure 7 Clips from the LiveSeeding video

3.8 Video booth with project experts

Another communication material of the project developed together with project partners is a series of short video materials (Figure 8). A series called "From Inspiration to Impact: A Project Expert's Story!" has been created to introduce experts involved in the project to the stakeholders. During the last annual meeting in Poznan (September 2023), a video booth was organized in the form of an interview, to collect stories from project partners about their work, expertise and involvement in the project. In total **12 short videos** were filmed and are continuously being published on the IPS YouTube channel and LiveSeeding social media channels. These videos have on average 50 views, and further involvement of other project experts in these videos is planned in the upcoming period of the project.

Videos on YouTube LiveSeeding playlist can be accessed by the following link: [LiveSeeding playlist](#).

A Project Expert's Story with M.Sc. Matteo Petitti

A Project Expert's Story with M.Sc. Freya Schäfer

Figure 8 Video series "A Project Expert's Story"

3.9 Articles for general media

One category of communication materials that will be produced during the project lifespan are articles for general media. Articles for general media are crucial in the projects such as LiveSeeding, as they raise public awareness and understanding of the research and its societal benefits. These articles help bridge the gap between scientific communities and the general public, making complex research accessible and engaging, thereby fostering broader support and engagement with the project's goals and outcomes. Articles that will be produced and published throughout the LiveSeeding project will target mainly 2 types of media:

1. Consumers magazines specialised in organic products, environment/nature and well-being read by « eco-citizens/consumers » (e.g. consumers magazine

by EcorNaturaSi in Italy or Coop magazine in Switzerland) and non-scientific/academic agro journals, and

2. Professional journals specialised in agricultural issues (e.g. Agrinnovation magazine, Bioaktuell in Switzerland) and for specific topics such as EU regulatory framework on organic seed policy in EU type magazines covering EU news and policy debates (e.g. Politico, Euronews).

At the time of writing of this deliverable, **7 articles** for general media have been published by project partners, 4 in Italy, 2 in Switzerland and one in Slovenia.

The List of currently published articles is provided in Table 1.

Table 1 Articles for general media published as part of the LiveSeeding project

Article	Magazine/journal title	Country	Partner
Spodbujanje trajnostnega kmetijstva z evropskim projektom LiveSeeding	Zelena Slovenija, ESG	Slovenia	KIS
Enhancing vegetable local varieties of Geneva	Rara	Switzerland	PSR
Article on participatory breeding project with support of the LiveSeeding project	Rara	Switzerland	PSR
Progetti LIVESEEDING	Coltiviamo la diversità #32, Notiziario di Rete Semi Rurali	Italy	RSR
Costruire sostenibilità dal campo alla tavola: 4 esperienze legate al progetto europeo LiveSeeding	Coltiviamo la diversità #33, Notiziario di Rete Semi Rurali	Italy	RSR
SeedLinked: uno strumento per prove varietali in biologico	Coltiviamo la diversità #34, Notiziario di Rete Semi Rurali	Italy	RSR
LIVESEEDING // RISO	coltiviamo la diversità #35, notiziario di rete semi rurali	Italy	RSR

4. Key communication channels

To effectively present project activities and results to stakeholders and the general public, LiveSeeding is using several communication channels:

- social media platforms - LinkedIn, Facebook, and X
- website
- newsletters
- YouTube channel of the Communication Coordinator

4.1 Social media channels

LiveSeeding regularly posts announcements about upcoming project events. (workshops, webinars, conferences, etc.) and provides reviews and articles about the conducted activities and project results on its social media channels and website (Table 2) to maximize the stakeholders engagement and to share up to date information on the project progress and outcomes with the target audience.

Table 2 LiveSeeding website and social media channels

LiveSeeding website:	https://liveseeding.eu/about-living-labs/
LiveSeeding X page:	https://x.com/LiveSeeding
LiveSeeding Facebook page:	https://www.facebook.com/LiveSeeding?locale=hr_HR
LiveSeeding LinkedIn profile:	https://www.linkedin.com/company/liveseeding-project/?viewAsMember=true

To increase the social media posts outreach and stakeholders' engagement, several post categories have been developed and are being published on these channels (Figure 8). List of regular social media posts sections:

- Meet the project partners
- Meet the project experts
- From the field
- Did you know?
- Glossary

At the time of writing this deliverable, LiveSeeding had **1926** followers on Facebook page, **1893** followers on X page and **299** followers on LinkedIn.

From the field

Gathering nearly 70 participants, our partners from ÖMKE - Ökológiai Mezőgazdasági Kutatóintézet held a field day in Szár, Hungary on 13 June 2024. 🌾

The field day focused on **organic cultivation** of cereals and variety selection. The visit included presentation of post-registration organic variety trials and durum wheat OHM populations studied in the framework of the LiveSeeding project.

Gyöngyi Györéné Kis, national L... Prikaži više

Did you know that to achieve 100% organic seed use in organic farming, it is estimated that we need to increase organic seed production six-fold over the next 10 years.

The LiveSeeding project brings together leading organisations from across the sector to help overcome the practice of derogations and make organic seed a reality across Europe. 🌱

We want to encourage organic farmers to buy high quality seeds that are resilient to adverse climatic conditions, promote biodiversity... Prikaži više

Figure 9 "From the field" and "Did you know?" type of posts

4.2 Website

LiveSeeding's website is designed in a simple and user-friendly way, It keeps stakeholders well-informed about project developments, offers a repository for accessing key project materials like press releases, videos, and publications, and acts as a promotional tool for upcoming events and training sessions. The website is regularly updated and maintained by Communication Coordinator.

Based on user feedback and our own experience over the past year and a half, we are planning several updates to further enhance the website's usability and effectiveness such as implementing a system for better content organization or reviewing existing submenus for content expansion and removal of empty ones.

At the time of writing this document, LiveSeeding website has reached a **total of 5 600 unique visitors**. More detailed information on the structure and elements of the project website, as well as the description of LiveSeeding social media channels are provided in the following deliverables · [D7.2 LiveSeeding Project website and social media](#) and D7.1 Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results (PEDR).

Figure 10 LiveSeeding website homepage

4.3 Newsletter

The main aim of the newsletter is to provide regular updates, information, and insights about the project's progress, activities, and results to the stakeholders. This includes announcements about upcoming events, summaries of recent activities, detailed reports on project milestones, and articles that offer a deeper understanding of the project's impact and achievements. The newsletter serves as a direct and efficient communication tool to keep stakeholders and the interested public informed and engaged with the project's developments.

The LiveSeeding newsletter is being prepared and circulated to subscribers twice a year throughout the project's duration, with a total of eight issues planned. The newsletters provide:

- Updates on project implementation and results;
- Relevant news from project partners;
- Information about project-related conferences, workshops, and trainings;
- Information about “sister” projects and the broader network of collaborations;
- Announcement of project events.

The newsletters are being uploaded to the project website and distributed to individuals who register for the newsletter via the website form (Figure 11) or through the broader stakeholder database (established as part of Task 7.3 by IFOAM OE) and are also shared by project partners via their social networks and websites.

3 project newsletters have been produced in the period covered by the present deliverable, with the last one covering the period until May 2024. The next newsletter (4th) is planned to be launched during October 2024. LiveSeeding newsletters are being prepared in the MailerLite app lead by the comms coordinator (IPS), and LiveSeeding subscription group has **488 members**. Project newsletters are published in pdf format on the LiveSeeding website under the [Newsletters](#) section.

Figure 11 Newsletter subscription letter

4.4 YouTube channel

YouTube channel of a Communication Coordinator (IPS) is used as a central point to broadcast all LiveSeeding videos to maximise visibility, views and SEO. A separate “LiveSeeding” playlist has been created (Figure 11).The Videos produced and published so far include: an official project video, a series “Project expert’s story”, and edited recordings of the workshops and webinars (OHM workshop, organic seed and planting material databases, Entrepreneurship in the organic seeds and breeding sector). LiveSeeding videos can be accessed on the following link [LiveSeeding playlist](#).

Figure 12 LiveSeeding playlist on YouTube channel

5. Key dissemination materials

LiveSeeding aims to generate and disseminate knowledge and its outcomes through various outputs and materials, and main dissemination materials include project deliverables, scientific publications, policy briefs and recommendations and practice abstracts.

Dissemination plays a crucial role in the LiveSeeding as an Innovation Action (IA) project, by ensuring that the knowledge and results generated are widely shared with relevant stakeholders. Therefore, dissemination materials enhance the visibility and impact of the project outcomes, promote the uptake of innovations, and facilitate the exchange of information between researchers, policymakers, industry, and the public. Effective dissemination strategies help to maximize the societal and economic benefits of the project, supporting the broader goals of the project.

5.1 Project’s deliverables

One of the key methods for disseminating project progress and results is through project deliverables. These deliverables are the outcomes of objective-focused work completed during the project, encompassing all outputs submitted within the project's scope. All non-confidential project deliverables will be uploaded to the project website. The primary target audience for these deliverables includes project agro-stakeholders (such as farmers, seed producers, and seed traders) and the research community. Throughout the project's lifespan, a total of **47 deliverables** will be produced.

Table 3 shows the list of public deliverables that have been produced at the time of writing of this deliverable, linked to the project website where they are deposited.

Table 3 List of published deliverables

D2.1	Platform for on-farm cultivar testing in EU accessible on web and mobile app stores
D6.1	Report on communication strategies, new narratives and science-based data on ecological, societal and economic benefits of organic breeding
D7.2	LiveSeeding project website and social media

5.2 Scientific publications

During the project's lifetime, at least **20 scientific publications**—including open access papers, book chapters, and posters—will be produced. The LiveSeeding project adheres to Horizon Europe's principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" regarding data and research outputs. Therefore, all scientific publications generated by the project will be published as Open Access, in accordance with the guidelines outlined in project deliverable D8.5 Data Management Plan.

Scientific publications are a crucial segment of dissemination as they disseminate research findings to the broader scientific community, fostering knowledge exchange and innovation. Furthermore, scientific publications enhance the visibility and impact of the project's outcomes, ensuring that the advancements drive further research and development.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, 3 scientific publications have been published as part of the LiveSeeding project. It should be taken into consideration that the process of data collection, analysis, and the subsequent peer-review process can be lengthy, and we anticipate more publications to follow as the project advances. These publications are published on Zenodo and are listed in the Table 4 below.

Table 4 List of scientific publications

	Title	Type	Authors
1.	Development and validation of molecular markers tagging anthracnose resistance in white lupin (<i>Lupinus albus</i>, L.)	Conference proceeding	Patyi, A., Schneider, M., Arncken, C., Messmer, M., Schwertfirm, G., Schweizer, G., & LAZZARO, M. (2023, June 19)
2.	Organic breeding of white lupin for regionally produced plant-based protein foods in Switzerland	Conference proceeding	Arncken, C., Messmer, M., Kretzschmar, U., Kamp, M., Kussmann, S., Patyi, A., & LAZZARO, M. (2023, June 19)
3.	LiveSeeding project - Insights into the opportunities and bottlenecks in organic seed and plant breeding sector	Conference proceeding	Maricic, D., & Spicnagel, A.-M. (2024, February 13)

5.3 Practice abstracts

Practice abstracts are of great importance in projects such as LiveSeeding, as they condense complex research findings into practical, actionable insights for practitioners such as farmers, seed producers, and agricultural consultants. They facilitate the direct application of innovative solutions in real-world settings, enhancing the impact and relevance of the research by addressing the immediate needs and challenges faced by end-users.

The knowledge generated from the LiveSeeding project will therefore be shared on the EU CAP Network (former EIP-AGRI) website for widespread dissemination to practitioners, following the EIP common format. Two sets of practice abstracts are planned in the project: the first batch, consisting of **five practice abstracts**, will be delivered by month 24 of the project as part of the Deliverable 7.5 "Practice Abstracts - batch 1", and the second batch, consisting of **ten practice abstracts**, will be delivered by month 48 as part of the Deliverable 7.7 "Practice Abstracts - batch 2". Each practice abstract will include a brief description of the objective and opportunities the project addresses, related to various aspects of organic seed and plant breeding, offering valuable resources for training and skill enhancement of the target groups. This follows the latest Guidelines for data on European Innovation Partnership Operational Groups.

Deliverable D7.5 - first batch of practice abstracts - is due in M24 (September 2024) and is planned to be submitted on time. accessible at the end of September 2024 over several repositories including Organic Farm Knowledge Platform, EU CAP Network website, as well as the LiveSeeding website.

Table 5 shows the list of topics of practice abstracts that will feed into the D7.5.

Table 5 Topics of practice abstracts from batch 1

WP4	<u>European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)</u>
WP2	<u>What is organic heterogeneous material (OHM), and how can it be notified?</u>
WP2	<u>Enhancing Organic Variety Development with SeedLinked: A Collaborative Digital Approach</u>
WP3	<u>DIY: Hot water treatment to sanitize vegetable seeds</u>
WP3	<u>Simple, non-destructive measurement of equilibrium Relative Humidity to evaluate seed moisture levels using a hygrometer</u>

5.4 Policy briefs

Policy briefs aim to disseminate knowledge to authorities and policymakers through presentations, recommendations and bilateral exchanges, and to promote strategies for organic seed and plant breeding. These briefs, based on outputs from various work packages as well as the long term expertise and scientific knowledge of partners acquired also in previous EU co-funded projects, will provide recommendations to European, national and regional authorities.

Two batches of policy briefs are planned in LiveSeeding project lifespan: the first batch, with **2 policy briefs** will be developed by month 36 and feed into the Deliverable 4.3 "Compilation of policy briefs on enabling strategies to promote organic seed and plant breeding covering different aspects - batch 1", and the second batch with **3 policy briefs** will be delivered in month 46 as part of the Deliverable 4.6 "Compilation of policy briefs on enabling strategies to promote organic seed and plant breeding covering different aspects - batch 2". Task 4.4, led by IFOAM OE with input from other project partners, is responsible for producing these briefs. Policy briefs will be uploaded to the LiveSeeding website, Organic e-Prints, and distributed through various channels.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, one policy brief has been published in April 2024 – "[EU reform on seed marketing regulation and its implications for the organic seed sector](#)" (Figure 12).

Figure 13 Front page of the 1st policy brief on the EU reform on seed marketing regulation

Policy Brief | April 2024
Adjusted version: September 2024

EU reform on seed marketing regulation from the perspective of organic breeders

Harmonizing science and policy to ensure stakeholder inclusion *

KEY POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

- ❑ The Organic Regulation 2018/848 should remain unchanged to guarantee legal certainty for the marketing of Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) and the definition of Organic Varieties suitable for organic production (OV).
- ❑ Value for Sustainable Cultivation and Use (VSCU) testing should be assessing the sustainability of a plant variety considering the specific conditions, geography and climatic conditions of a given system and it should not be expanded to vegetable and fruit crops.
- ❑ Instead of mandatory VSCU testing of arable crops, frugal post-release on-farm testing networks should be considered.
- ❑ Registration of Organic Varieties (OV) should be promoted by DUS tests, with less strict requirements regarding Uniformity, and VSCU testing should be conducted under organic farming conditions by national examination offices or by organic breeders under official supervision.
- ❑ Diversity varieties combining traditionally grown as well as newly developed varieties can be registered without DUS testing, provided that they have an officially recognized description, and no limitation on packaging size or geographic region.
- ❑ Organic Varieties, Heterogeneous Material and Diversity Varieties should remain free from genetically modified organism (GMO) and new genomic techniques (NGT), and all PRM should be free from patents in order to allow farmers' privilege and breeders' exemptions.
- ❑ There should be full transparency on cultivar types and breeding techniques applied.
- ❑ To live up to the principles of the "Better Regulations" agenda, administrative burdens need to be minimized. Organic stakeholders need to be involved in the development of delegated and implementing acts for the marketing of PRM to achieve the goal of 25% organic farmland in the European Union (EU) by 2030.

LiveSeeding is a Horizon Europe co-funded Innovation project aiming to foster the growth of the organic sector by delivering high-quality organic seeds of diverse cultivars adjusted to organic farming for a wide range of crops.

LiveSeeding brings together 37 research institutions, seed producers, plant breeders, farmers, processors and consumers, covering the whole value chain.

We welcome the draft regulation on production and marketing of plant reproductive material published in July 2023 and suggest following amendments based on extensive scientific research, field experience and sectoral expertise.

* Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of individual Project Consortium members, of the European Union or REA, nor SERI or UKRE.

Annex I Templates

Enter Document Title Here

Authors: **First name Last name (Organisation)**
 First name Last name (Organisation)
 First name Last name (Organisation)
 First name Last name (Organisation)

Deliverable Number	DX.X
Work Package	WPX
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Confidential/Classified/Public
Deliverable Lead partner	Organisation's acronym
Due date	
Submission date	
Version	
Reviewers	
Contact	

Funded by the European Union (grant no. 101059872), the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (Contract no. 22.0412) and UK Research and Innovation (LRI). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA, nor SERL or LRI.

Submission date	
Version	
Reviewers	
Contact	

History of changes

Version	Date	Author	Comments

LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards *environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems* through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE strategy** to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),

- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

1. Table of Contents

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ANNEX 1	6

2. List of abbreviations

1. Heading 1

1.1 Heading 2

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1.1.1.1 Heading 4

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 - Subitem 1
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 - Subitem 4

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Info Box

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Figure 3: Please add your text below figure, no point at the end

Figure 4: Please add your text below figure, no point at the end

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LiveSeeding_source (Indicate the source of a figure or table)

Hyperlink: www.

References

LiveSeeding_references – see example below

- Willer, H., Schlatter, B., Travnicek, J., Kemper, L., Lamoud, J. "The World of Organic Agriculture. Statistics and Emerging Trends 2020". Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, and IFOAM – Organics International, Bonn, January 28, 2020. Accessed June 10, 2024. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/37222/9/willer-et-al-2020-full-document-2020-02-28-4th-corrigenda.pdf>

Deliverable template

Type of the Event

„Title of the Event“

About the event

 Date

 Time

 Place

Register
now/Save
date the

Funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

EVENT INVITE HEADLINE

5 – 7 December 2022

Online event

Register today:

www.liveseeding.com/event

Funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA, nor SERI or UKRI.

Event invite templates

Annex II Project leaflet in consortium languages

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About

LIVESEEDING is 4-year Innovation Action. It aims to **promote the growth of organic seed and plant breeding** for the transition to more sustainable local food systems. It is providing science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help the sector to achieve the target of 100 % organic seed use in organic farming by 2036!

Project Coordinator: FiBL Europe
Scientific Coordinator: FiBL-CH

Duration: Oct 22 - Sept 26
Budget: 6.6 m €

Funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) (contract number 23.0412) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Who is involved?

To deliver on such an ambitious goal, LiveSeeding brings together **37 organizations** covering whole value chain. This includes public and private research institutions and universities, seed producers, plant breeders, farmers, decision-makers and public authorities, processors and consumers operating in **16 European countries**.

English

Push-Pull-Enable methodology

Our work combines activities that increase both the **supply** (PUSH) and **demand** (PULL) of organic seeds and cultivars across the sector and feeds into the development of an enabling **policy environment** (ENABLE).

Innovative approach

LiveSeeding follows a holistic, multi-actor and participatory approach. Various stakeholders are involved through:

- **17 LIVING LABS** bringing together breeders, consumers and citizens
- **3 established networks** of Organic Breeders (ECO-PB), Seed Savers and Community seed banks (ECLLD), and cities members of Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP).

Zaprati nas na

LiveSeeding www.liveseeding.eu
 @LiveSeeding LiveSeeding

O projektu

LIVESEEDING je četverogodišnji projekt u okviru programa Obzor Europa „Inovacijske aktivnosti“ čiji je cilj **promicanje rasta ekološke proizvodnje sjemena i oplemenjivanja bilja** radi prijelaza na održivije lokalne prehrambene sustave. Projekt pruža znanstveno utemeljene dokaze i rješenja kako bi pomogao sektoru da postigne cilj upotrebe 100 % ekološkog sjemena u ekološkoj poljoprivredi do 2036 godine!

Promijeni sjeme, napravi razliku!

Financira Europska unija, Švicarsko državno tajništvo za obrazovanje, istraživanje i inovacije (SERI Ugovor br. 22.0412) i UK istraživanje i inovacije (LIFE). Tekst izlaza isključivo stavovi i mišljenja autora i ne odražava nužno stavove i mišljenja Europske unije ili SERI ili UK.

Projektni koordinator: FiBL Europe
 Znanstveni koordinator: FiBL-CH

Trajanje: listopad 2022. - studeni 2026.
 Budžet: 6.6 mil. €

Tko je uključen?

Uključene su javne i privatne istraživačke ustanove i sveučilišta, proizvođači sjemena, oplemenjivači bilja, poljoprivrednici, nadležna tijela, prerađivači te potrošači koji djeluju u **16 europskih zemalja**.

Slovenian

Metodologija "Push-Pull Enable"

Naš rad objedinjuje aktivnosti koje povećavaju i **ponudu** (PUSH) i **potražnju** (PULL) za ekološkim sjemenom i kultivarima u sektoru te doprinose stvaranju poticajnog **političkog/zakonodavnog** okruženja (ENABLE).

Inovativan pristup

LiveSeeding se temelji na cjelovitom, višestranom i participativnom pristupu tematici te uključuje različite dionike:

- **17 "ŽIVIH LABORATORIJA"** (eng. LIVING LABS) koji okupljaju oplemenjivače bilja, potrošače i građane
- **3 uspostavljene mreže** ekoloških oplemenjivača (ECO-PB), čuvara sjemena (ECLLD) i Milanski pakt za urbanu prehrambenu politiku (MUFPP)

Suivez-nous sur:

A propos de

LIVSEEDING est un projet de recherche-action d'une durée de 4 ans qui vise à **promouvoir le développement des semences et de la sélection variétale biologiques**, pour une transition vers des systèmes alimentaires locaux plus durables. Il fournit des preuves scientifiques et de bonnes pratiques pour aider à atteindre l'objectif de 100 % de semences biologiques dans l'agriculture biologique d'ici 2036 !

Financé par l'Union européenne, le Secrétariat d'Etat suisse à la formation, à la recherche et à l'innovation (numéro de contrat SERI 22.0412) et UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Coordinateur du projet: FIBL Europe
 Coordinateur scientifique: FIBL-CH

Durée: Oct 22 - Sept 26
 Budget: 6.6 m €

Qui est impliqué?

Pour atteindre cet objectif ambitieux, LiveSeeding rassemble **37 organisations** couvrant l'ensemble de la chaîne de valeur : universités et instituts de recherche publiques et privées, producteurs de semences et sélectionneurs de cultivars, consommateurs, décideurs et autorités publiques opérant dans **16 pays européens**.

French

Une méthodologie « Push-Pull-Enable »

Notre travail intègre des activités qui stimulent à la fois **la demande** (PULL) et **l'offre** de semences et de cultivars biologiques (PUSH) tout au long de la chaîne de valeur, en aval (sélectionneurs, agriculteurs, producteurs de semences) et en amont (transformateurs, détaillants, marchés locaux, citoyens), soutenues par un **cadre réglementaire favorable** (ENABLE).

Une approche innovante

LiveSeeding travaille avec une approche holistique, multi-acteurs et participative. Diverses parties prenantes sont impliquées par le biais de :

- **17 «LIVING LABS»** réunissant des sélectionneurs, des agriculteurs, des consommateurs et des citoyens
- **3 réseaux établis** de sélectionneurs et producteurs de semences biologiques (ECO-PB), de collectifs citoyens et paysans et de maisons des semences paysannes[1] (ECLLD) et de villes adhérentes au Pacte de Milan pour une politique alimentaire urbaine (MUFPF).

Kövess minket:

Rólunk

A LIVESEEDING egy 4 éves innovációs intézkedés. Célja az **ökológiai vetőmagtermesztés, illetve növénynemesítés** széleskörű elterjesztése a fenntarthatóbb helyi élelmiszerrendszerek kialakítása érdekében. Tudományosan megalapozott bizonyítékokkal és példamutató gyakorlati megoldásokkal segíti a szektort abban, hogy a 2036-ra kitűzött 100%-os ökológiai vetőmaghasználatot sikerüljön elérnie az ökológiai gazdálkodásban.

Készült az Európai Unió, a Svéd Országos Kutatói és Innovációs Alkalmazás (SRI) felhívás (22.042), valamint az Egyesült Királyság Kutatói és Innovációs Hozzájárulás (UKRI) támogatásával.

Projektkoordinátor: FiBL Europe
Tudományos koordinátor: FiBL-CH

Időtartam: 2022. Október – 2026. Szeptember
Költségvetés: 6,6 millió €

Kik a résztvevők?

Az ambiciózus cél elérése érdekében a LiveSeeding **37 szervezetet** kapcsol össze, melyek a teljes értékláncot lefedik. Vannak közöttük állami és magán-kutatóintézetek, illetve egyetemek, vetőmagtermelők, növénynemesítők, gazdálkodók, döntéshozók, hatóságok, feldolgozók, valamint fogyasztók összesen **16 európai országból**.

Hungarian

Push-Pull-Enable módszer

A munkánk olyan tevékenységeket kombinál, amelyek az ökológiai vetőmagok és fajták piacának **kínálati (PUSH)**, illetve **keresleti (PULL)** oldalát is növelik a szektoron belül, továbbá egy támogató politikai környezet (ENABLE) kialakítását ösztönzik.

Innovatív megközelítés

A LiveSeeding holisztikus, sokszereplős és részvételen alapuló megközelítést alkalmaz. Különböző érintettek vesznek részt a munkában az alábbi formában:

- **17 ÉLŐ LABORATÓRIUM** kapcsolja össze a nemesítőket, a fogyasztókat és a lakosságot
- **3 működő hálózaton** keresztül: Európai Ökológiai Növénynemesítők Szervezete (ECO-PB), Európai Közöségi Magbankok Hálózata (ECLLD), és a Milánói Városi Élelmiszer-Politikai Paktumot (MUFPP) aláíró városok.

 Volg ons op:

Over

LIVESEEDING is een 4-jarig Innovatie Actie project, die de groei van de biologische zaad en plantenveredingssector wil bevorderen voor de overgang naar duurzame lokale voedselsystemen. Het project levert wetenschappelijk onderbouwd bewijs en praktijkoplossingen om de doelstelling van 100% biologisch zaad in 2036 te helpen bereiken!

Gefinancierd door de Europese Unie, het Zwitserse staatssecretariaat voor onderwijs, onderzoek en innovatie (SERI contractnummer 22.0412) en UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Projectcoördinator FiBL Europe
Wetenschappelijke coördinator: FiBL-CH

Duur: Oct 22 - Sept 26
Budget: 6.6 m €

Wie is betrokken?

Om dit ambitieuze doel te bereiken, verenigt LiveSeeding **37 organisaties** die de hele waardeketen bestrijken; zoals publieke en private onderzoeksinstituten en universiteiten, zaadproducenten en plantenveredelaars, beslissers, overheden, verwerkers en consumenten, die actief zijn in **16 Europese landen**.

Dutch

Push-Pull-Enable methodologie

Deze methodologie combineert activiteiten die zowel het aanbod van (PUSH) als de vraag naar (PULL) biologische zaden en cultivars vergroten, ondersteund door een gunstig beleidsklimaat (ENABLE).

Innovatieve aanpak

LiveSeeding werkt volgens een holistische, multi-actor en participatieve aanpak. Verschillende belanghebbenden zijn betrokken via:

- **17 LIVING LABS** die veredelaars, consumenten en burgers samenbrengen
- **3 gevestigde netwerken** van biologische veredelaars (ECO-PB), Seed Savers en Community seed banks (ECLLD) en bij het Milan.

Śledź nas na:

0 projekcie

LIVESEEDING to 4-letni projekt innowacyjny, którego celem jest **promowanie rozwoju produkcji ekologicznego materiału siewnego i ekologicznej hodowli roślin** aby osiągnąć zrównoważenie i zróżnicowanie systemów żywnościowych w Europie. Projekt dostarcza dowodów naukowych i rozwiązań opartych na najlepszych praktykach, aby pomóc osiągnąć cel 100% ekologicznego materiału siewnego do 2036 roku!

Projekt dofinansowany przez Unię Europejską, Szwajcarski Sekretariat Stanu ds. Edukacji, Badań i Innowacji (numer umowy SERI 22.04.12) oraz Badania i Innowacje Wschodniej Brytanii (UKRI). Wyrazona podjęty i opiera się jedynie wyłącznie na poglądach autorów i niekoniecznie odzwierciedla poglądy Unii Europejskiej, REA, SERI czy UKRI.

Koordinator projektu: FIBL Europe
Koordinator naukowy: FIBL-CH

Okres realizacji: 10.2022-09.2026
Budżet: 6.6 mln €

Kto jest zaangażowany?

Aby zrealizować tak ambitny cel, LiveSeeding zrzesza **37 organizacji** obejmujących cały łańcuch wartości, od instytucji badawczych po producentów nasion, hodowców roślin i konsumentów, działających w **16 krajach europejskich**.

Polish

Metodologia Push-Pull-Enable

łączy działania, które zwiększają zarówno **popyt** (PULL), jak i **podaż** (PUSH) ekologicznych nasion i odmian w całym łańcuchu wartości w dół (hodowcy, rolnicy, producenci nasion) i w górę (przetwórcy, detaliści, rynki lokalne, obywatele), co jest wspierane przez sprzyjające **środowisko polityczne** (ENABLE).

Innowacyjne podejście

Podejście LiveSeeding ma charakter holistyczny, wielopodmiotowy i partycypacyjny. Różni interesariusze są zaangażowani poprzez:

- **17 ŻYWYCH LABORATORIÓW** skupiających hodowców, konsumentów i obywateli
- **3 ustanowione sieci** hodowców ekologicznych (ECO-PB), oszczędzających nasiona (ECLLD) i Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP).

Siga-nos em:

Sobre

O LIVESEEDING é um projeto de Inovação e Ação de 4 anos de duração. Tem como objetivo **promover o aumento de sementes biológicas** e do melhoramento de plantas biológico para a transição para sistemas alimentares locais mais sustentáveis. Assenta em evidências de base científica e soluções recorrendo às melhores práticas para ajudar a alcançar a meta de 100% de sementes biológicas na agricultura biológica até 2036!

 Financiado pela União Europeia, pela Secretaria de Estado Sulgo da Educação, Investigação e Inovação (número de contrato 22.0412) e pela UE - Investigação e Inovação (ERDF).

 Coordenador do projeto: FiBL Europa
 Coordenador científico: FiBL-CH

Duração Out 22 - Set 26
 Orçamento: 6.6 m €

Quem está envolvido?

Para alcançar um objetivo tão ambicioso, o LIVESEEDING reúne **37 organizações** que abrangem toda a cadeia de valor, desde universidades e instituições de investigação públicas e privadas, produtores de sementes/melhoradores de plantas e agricultores, a transformadores, autoridades públicas e consumidores, operando em **16 países europeus**.

Portuguese

Metodologia "Push-Pull-Enable"

A metodologia "Push-Pull-Enable" combina atividades que aumentam tanto a **procura** (PULL) quanto o **fornecimento** (PUSH) de sementes biológicas e cultivares ao longo da cadeia de valor a montante (melhoradores, agricultores, produtores de sementes) e a jusante (processadores, retalhistas, mercados locais, cidadãos), apoiada por um **contexto jurídico favorável** (ENABLE).

Abordagem inovadora

O LiveSeeding trabalha com uma abordagem holística, multiator e participativa. Vários interessados estão envolvidos por meio de:

- **17 Laboratórios Vivos** que reúnem melhoradores de plantas, consumidores e cidadãos.
- **3 redes existentes** de Melhoradores de Plantas Biológicos (ECO-PB), Guardiões e Bancos Comunitários de Sementes (ECLLD) e cidades membros do Pacto de Política Alimentar Urbana de Milão (MUFPF).

Urmați-ne pe:

LiveSeeding www.liveseeding.eu
 @LiveSeeding LiveSeeding

Despre

LIVESEEDING este o Acțiune de Inovare pe 4 ani. Obiectivul este promovarea semințelor și a ameliorării ecologice a plantelor pentru sisteme alimentare locale. Furnizează rezultate bazate pe metode științifice și cele mai bune soluții practice pentru a ajuta sectorul să atingă ținta de utilizare a semințelor ecologice până în 2036!

Finanțat de Uniunea Europeană, Secretariatul Statului Elvețian pentru Educație, Cercetare și Inovare (numărul de contract SERI 22.0412) și UK Research și Inovare (UKRI).

Coordonator de proiect FiBL Europe

Coordonator științific: FiBL-CH

Durata: Oct 22 - Sept 26

Buget: 6.6 m €

Cine sunt implicați?

Pentru a oferi răspunsul acestui obiectiv ambițios, LiveSeeding aduce împreună **37 de organizații** care acoperă lanțul valoric în întregime. Acesta include instituții de cercetare publice și private, universități producători de sămânță, amelioratori, fermieri, factori de decizie și autorități publice, procesatori și consumatori care lucrează în **16 țări Europene**.

Romanian

Metodologia Push-Pull-Enable

Activitatea noastră combină acțiuni care cresc atât oferta (PUSH) cât și cererea (PULL) semințelor și cultivarelor ecologice din sector și influențează dezvoltarea unui mediu politic favorabil (ENABLE).

Abordare inovativă

LiveSeeding urmărește o abordare holistică, multi-actori, prin abordare participativă. Actori diverși sunt implicați în:

- **17 LABORATORE VII** aduc împreună amelioratori, consumatori și cetățeni
- **3 rețele stabilite** de Amelioratori Ecologici (ECO-PB), Salvatori de Semințe și Bănci de gene ale comunității (ECLLD) și membrii ai comunităților urbane ai Pactului Milanez Urban pentru Politica Alimentației (MUFPP).

Ακολουθήστε μας στο:

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 @LiveSeeding LiveSeeding

Σχετικά με το

Το LIVESEEDING είναι μια Δράση Καινοτομίας διάρκειας 4 ετών, η οποία αποσκοπεί στην **προώθηση της ανάπτυξης του βιολογικού σπόρου και της οργανικής βελτίωσης φυτών** για τη μετάβαση σε ποσειφορικά τοπικά συστήματα διατροφής. Παρέχει επιστημονικά τεκμηριωμένα στοιχεία και λύσεις βέλτιστης πρακτικής για να βοηθήσει στην επίτευξη του στόχου του 100% βιολογικού σπόρου μέχρι το 2036!

Κοινοτομείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση, την Ελβετική Κρατική Γραμματεία για την Επιστήμη, την Έρευνα και την Καινοτομία (SEF) αριθμός σύμβασης: 22.04121 και το UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Συντονιστής έργου: FiBL Ευρώπη
Επιστημονικός συντονιστής: FiBL-CH

Διάρκεια: 22 Οκτωβρίου- 26 Σεπτεμβρίου
Προϋπολογισμός: 6,6 εκατ. ευρώ

Ποιος εμπλέκεται?

Για την επίτευξη ενός τόσο φιλόδοξου στόχου, το LiveSeeding φέρνει κοντά **37 οργανισμούς** που καλύπτουν ολόκληρη την αλυσίδα αξίας, από τα ερευνητικά ιδρύματα έως τους παραγωγούς σπόρων/βελτιωτές και τους καταναλωτές, οι οποίοι δραστηριοποιούνται σε **16 Ευρωπαϊκές χώρες**.

Greek

Μεθοδολογία Push-Pull-Enable

Το έργο μας συνδυάζει δραστηριότητες που αυξάνουν τόσο τη **ζήτηση (PULL)** όσο και την **προσφορά (PUSH)** βιολογικών σπόρων και καλλιεργειών σε όλη την αλυσίδα αξίας προς τα κάτω (βελτιωτές, γεωργούς, παραγωγούς σπόρων) και προς τα πάνω (μεταποιητές, λιανοπωλητές, τοπικές αγορές, πολίτες), υποστηριζόμενες από ένα **ευνοϊκό πολιτικό περιβάλλον (ENABLE)**.

Καινοτόμος προσέγγιση

Το LiveSeeding ακολουθεί μια ολιστική, πολυπαραγοντική και συμμετοχική προσέγγιση. Συμμετέχουν διάφοροι φορείς μέσω:

- **17 ΣΩΝΤΑΝΩΝ ΕΡΓΑΣΤΗΡΙΩΝ** που φέρνουν σε επαφή βελτιωτές, καταναλωτές και πολίτες
- **3 καθιερωμένους δικτύων:** των Οργανικών Βελτιωτών (ECO-PB), των Διατηρητών Σπόρων (ECLLD), Κοινοτικές Τράπεζες Σπόρων και το Σύμφωνο Αστικής Πολιτικής Τροφίμων του Μιλάνου (MUFPP).

Folgen Sie uns auf:

LiveSeeding www.liveseeding.eu
 @LiveSeeding LiveSeeding

Über uns

LIVSEEDING ist eine vierjährige Innovationsaktion, die darauf abzielt, **das Wachstum von ökologischem Saatgut und ökologischer Pflanzenzucht** für den Übergang zu nachhaltigeren lokalen Lebensmittelsystemen zu fördern. Sie liefert wissenschaftlich fundierte Erkenntnisse und Best-Practice-Lösungen, die helfen sollen, das Ziel von 100 % ökologischem Saatgut im ökologischen Landbau bis 2036 zu erreichen!

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union, dem Schweizer Staatssekretariat für Bildung, Forschung und Innovation (SERI-Vertragsnummer 22.0412) und UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). **Projektkoordinatorin:** FiBL Europe **Wissenschaftskordinatorin:** FiBL-CH **Dauer:** Okt 22 - Sept 26 **Haushalt:** 6.6 m €

Wer ist beteiligt?

Um dieses anspruchsvolle Ziel zu erreichen, bringt LiveSeeding **37 Organisationen** aus **16 europäischen Ländern** zusammen, die die gesamte Wertschöpfungskette abdecken, von Forschungseinrichtungen und Universitäten über Saatguterzeuger/Pflanzenzüchter und Landwirte bis hin zu den Verbrauchern.

German

Push-Pull-Enable-Methodik

Unsere Arbeit kombiniert Aktivitäten, die sowohl **die Nachfrage (PULL)** als auch **das Angebot (PUSH)** von ökologischem Saatgut und Kultursorten in der nachgelagerten (Züchter, Landwirte, Saatgutproduzenten) und vorgelagerten (Verarbeiter, Einzelhändler, lokale Märkte, Bürger) Wertschöpfungskette erhöhen, unterstützt durch **ein günstiges politisches Umfeld (ENABLE)**.

Innovativer Ansatz

LiveSeeding arbeitet mit einem holistischen, akteursübergreifenden und partizipativen Konzept. Verschiedene Interessengruppen sind beteiligt durch:

- **17 REALLABORE** die Züchter, Verbraucher und Bürger zusammenbringen
- **3 etablierte Netzwerke** von Bio-Züchtern (ECO-PB), Seed Savers (ECLLD) und dem »Mailänder Abkommen über städtische Ernährungspolitik« (Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP)).

 Seguiteci su:

A proposito

LIVESEEDING è un progetto innovativo della durata di 4 anni. Mira a **promuovere la crescita di sementi e colture biologiche** per la transizione verso un sistema alimentare locale più sostenibile. Fornisce evidenze scientifiche e migliori soluzioni pratiche al fine di aiutare il settore a raggiungere l'obiettivo di utilizzare il 100% di sementi biologiche in agricoltura biologica entro il 2036!

Finanziato dall'Unione Europea, dalla Segreteria di Stato Svizzera per l'istruzione, Ricerca e Innovazione (SERI) numero di contratto 22.0432 e Ricerca e innovazione del Regno Unito (UKRI).

Coordinatore del Progetto: FiBL Europe
Coordinatore scientifico: FiBL-CH

Durata: Ottobre 2022 – Settembre 2026
Budget: 6.6 mio €

Chi è coinvolto?

Per raggiungere un obiettivo così ambizioso, LiveSeeding riunisce **37 organizzazioni** che coprono l'intera catena del valore. Si tratta di istituzioni di ricerca pubbliche e private, università, produttori di sementi, breeders, agricoltori, autorità pubbliche, trasformatori e consumatori che operano in **16 paesi Europei**.

Italian

Metodologia "Push-Pull-Enable"

Il nostro lavoro combina attività che aumentano sia l'**offerta** (PUSH) che la **domanda** (PULL) di sementi e varietà biologiche in tutto il settore, contribuendo allo sviluppo di un **contesto politico favorevole** (ENABLE).

Approccio innovativo

LiveSeeding segue un approccio olistico, multi-attore e partecipativo. I vari soggetti interessati sono coinvolti attraverso:

- **17 LIVING LABS** che riuniscono breeders, consumatori e cittadini
- **3 reti consolidate** di breeders biologici (ECO-PB), banche semi comunitarie (ECLLD) e Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPF) un patto internazionale sottoscritto da 260 città di tutto il mondo.

Zaprti nas na

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LiveSeeding
 Transformacija sektora ekološkog sjemenarstva

O projektu

LIVESEEDING je četverogodišnji projekt u okviru programa Obzor Europa „Inovacijske aktivnosti“ čiji je cilj **promicanje rasta ekološke proizvodnje sjemena i oplemenjivanja bilja** radi prijelaza na održivije lokalne prehrambene sustave. Projekt pruža znanstveno utemeljene dokaze i rješenja kako bi pomogao sektoru da postigne cilj upotrebe 100 % ekološkog sjemena u ekološkoj poljoprivredi do 2036 godine!

Financira: Evropska unija, Švicarsko državno tijelo za obrazovanje, istraživanje i inovacije (SERI Upravitelj: 22.0812) i UK istraživanje i inovacije (UKRI). Tekst izlaskava isključivo stavove i mišljenja autora i ne odražava nužno stavove i mišljenja Evropske unije ili REA i SERI ili UKRI.

Projektni koordinator: FiBL Europe
 Znanstveni koordinator: FiBL-CH

Trajanje: listopad 2022. - studeni 2026.
 Budžet: 6.6 mil. €

Tko je uključen?

Uključene su javne i privatne istraživačke ustanove i sveučilišta, proizvođači sjemena, oplemenjivači bilja, poljoprivrednici, nadležna tijela, prerađivači te potrošači koji djeluju u **16 europskih zemalja**.

Croatian

Metodologija "Push-Pull Enable"

Naš rad objedinjuje aktivnosti koje povećavaju i **ponudu** (PUSH) i **potražnju** (PULL) za ekološkim sjemenom i kultivarima u sektoru te doprinose stvaranju poticajnog **političkog/zakonodavnog** okruženja (ENABLE).

Inovativan pristup

LiveSeeding se temelji na cjelovitom, višestranom i participativnom pristupu tematici te uključuje različite dionike:

- **17 "ŽIVIH LABORATORIJA"** (eng. LIVING LABS) koji okupljaju oplemenjivače bilja, potrošače i građane
- **3 uspostavljene mreže** ekoloških oplemenjivača (ECO-PB), čuvara sjemena (ECLLD) i Milanski pakt za urbanu prehrambenu politiku (MUFPP)

Annex III Project roll up in consortium languages

LiveSeeding
Transforming organic seed systems

- 4 years
- 6,6 Mio €
- 15 focus crops
- 37 partners
- 17 Living Labs
- 16 countries

Change seed, grow difference!

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 www.liveseeding.eu

Funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI contract number 22.0412) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

English

LiveSeeding

Transformarea sistemelor de
semințe ecologice

LiveSeeding
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 LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Finanțat de Uniunea Europeană, Secretariatul Statului Elvețian pentru Educație, Cercetare și Inovare (numărul de contract SERI 22.0412) și UK Cercetare și Inovare (UKRI).

LiveSeeding

Cambiamo i sistemi sementieri bio

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Italian v1

LiveSeeding

Cambiamo i sistemi sementieri bio

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 LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Cofinanziato dall'Unione europea. Le opinioni espresse appartengono, tuttavia, ai soli autori e non riflettono necessariamente le opinioni dell'Unione europea, di SERI o UKRI*

Italian v2

LiveSeeding

Transformando os sistemas de produção de semente biológica

LiveSeeding
 @LiveSeeding

 LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Financiado pela União Europeia, pela Secretaria de Estado Suíça da Educação, Investigação e Inovação (número de contrato SERI 22.0412) e pelo UK - Investigação e Inovação (UKRI).

Portuguese

LiveSeeding

Transformatie van biologische
zaadsystemen

LiveSeeding
 @LiveSeeding

LiveSeeding
www.liveseeding.eu

Medegefinancierd door de Europese Unie

Funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI contract number 22.0412) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

UK Research and Innovation

Dutch

LiveSeeding

Μετασχηματίζοντας τα
συστήματα βιολογικού
σπόρου

LiveSeeding
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 LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Χρηματοδοτείται από την Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση, την Ελβετική Κρατική Γραμματεία Εκπαίδευσης, Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας (αριθμός σύμβασης SERI 22.0412) και το UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Greek

LiveSeeding

Umgestaltung von Ökologischen
Saatgutssystemen

LiveSeeding
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LiveSeeding
www.liveseeding.eu

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union, dem Schweizer Staatssekretariat für Bildung, Forschung und Innovation (SERI-Vertragsnummer 22.0412) und UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

German

LiveSeeding

Zmieniamy system nasiennictwa ekologicznego

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 LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Co-funded by the European Union
 Projekt dofinansowany przez Unię Europejską, Szwajcarski Sekretariat Stanu ds. Edukacji, Badań i Innowacji (numer umowy SERI 22.0412) oraz Badania i Innowacje Wielkiej Brytanii (UKRI).

Polish

LiveSeeding

Preoblikovanje sistemov v pridelavi ekološkega semena

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LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Financirajo Evropska unija, Švicarski državni sekretariat za izobraževanje, raziskave in inovacije (pogodba SERI št. 22.0412) in Raziskave in inovacije v Veliki Britaniji (UKRI).

UK Research and Innovation

Slovenian

LiveSeeding

Transformación y mejora de los sistemas agroecológicos y de la disponibilidad de semillas ecológicas

LiveSeeding
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LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Financiado por la Unión Europea, la Secretaría de Estado de Educación, Investigación e Innovación de Suiza (contrato SERI número 22.0412) y UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Spanish v1

LiveSeeding

Transformación y mejora de los sistemas y la disponibilidad de semillas ecológicas

LiveSeeding
 @LiveSeeding
 LiveSeeding
 www.liveseeding.eu

Financiado por la Unión Europea, la Secretaría de Estado de Educación, Investigación e Innovación de Suiza (contrato SERI número 22.0412) y UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Spanish v2

Annex IV Project pitch

LiveSeeding works with a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in:

- **17 local Living Labs** (LLs), where innovation will be co-generated involving the whole value chain, from breeders to consumers and citizens;
- **3 established networks** of: organic breeders (ECO-PB), seed savers (ECLLD), and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP).

15 focus crops will be used **within LivingLabs** in breeding, cultivar testing and seed production, namely: 4 cereals (wheat, rice, oat, maize) and 1 pseudo-cereal (buck-wheat), 1 oilseed crop (sunflower), 4 grain legumes (broad bean, lupin, beans and soybean), 4 vegetables (pepper, carrot, tomato and brassica) and 1 fodder (alfalfa).

These activities take place in **15 European countries** covering different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in Eastern and Southern Europe.

To learn more about the project please visit our website and follow up on our social media channels:

www.liveseeding.eu

<https://twitter.com/LIVESEEDING>

<https://www.facebook.com/LIVESEEDING/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/liveseeding-project/>